

D8.1 Project website

WP8

Lead Partner: FENIX

Dissemination Level: PU

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Deliverable Version: V1

Project Acronym	EnDurCrete
Project Title	New Environmental friendly and Durable conCrete, integrating industrial by-products and hybrid systems, for civil, industrial and offshore applications
Grant Agreement n°	760639
Funding Scheme	Research Innovation Action
Call	H2020-NMBP-2017
Topic	NMBP-06-2017 Improved material durability in buildings and infrastructures, including offshore
Starting Date	1 st January 2018
Duration	42 Months

Executive Summary

The Deliverable D8.1 Project website is a public document of the EnDurCrete project, delivered in the context of WP8 Training, dissemination and exploitation, Task 8.1 Dissemination, Communication and Networking. The objective of Task 8.1 is to secure the successful dissemination through the implementation and deployment of an awareness and dissemination plan. This document presents the first step in the partial objective of developing and deploying an awareness and dissemination plan: the EnDurCrete project website (accessed at www.endurcrete.eu) dedicated to the wide public audience all around the world.

Table of Contents

1	Introduction	7
2	Design and registration data	8
3	Website description	10
3.1	Home page	10
3.2	“About the project” page	11
3.3	“Documents” page	12
3.4	“News & Events” page	14
3.5	Partners	14
3.6	“Contact” page	15
3.7	Reserved area	15
3.8	Social network links and Newsletter subscription	17
3.9	Cookies policy	17
3.10	Working with the website	18
4	Future development	19
5	Conclusions and recommendations	20

List of Figures

Figure 1: Webhosting registration data.....	8
Figure 2: Domain registration data.....	9
Figure 3: Home page section	11
Figure 4: About project section	12
Figure 5: Public documents section.....	13
Figure 6: News & Events section	14
Figure 7: Partners section.....	14
Figure 8: Partners section - detail.....	15
Figure 9: Contact section	15
Figure 10: Reserved Area section – Login.....	16
Figure 11: Reserved Area - Restricted files.....	16
Figure 12: Social media and Newsletter subscription	17
Figure 13: Cookies policy	17
Figure 14: Working with the website Schema.....	18

Abbreviations and Acronyms

[WP] – Work Package

[D] – Deliverable

[html] – HyperText Markup Language

[php] – Hypertext Preprocessor

1 Introduction

First step determining the visual identity of the project was developing a project logo. Once it was ready an entire website was constructed utilizing the visual identity. The website is available online and can be accessed at www.endurcrete.eu. The website is intended to be dynamic. News & Events section as well as the rest of the content will be updated at least once a month and managed by the Dissemination WP leader (FENIX) throughout the lifetime of the project based on the partners' inputs and project evolution. The information published at the website will be presented in a way that is accessible and understandable by wide range of stakeholders.

An initial version of the EnDurCrete project website has been designed, provisioned and deployed on the Internet. It has been designed to quickly address the key questions that external visitors to the website are expected to have:

- What is the project about?
- What is the project progress?
- Who is participating in the project?
- What additional details are available?
- Who to contact for more information?

The site is hosted by WP8 leader (FENIX), under the domain www.endurcrete.eu. Google Analytics as a key performance indicator has been considered and deployed at this early stage of the project (e.g. users, countries of origin, languages, browsers, devices, etc.). Website was designed considering display on different devices such as desktop, mobile or tablet.

2 Design and registration data

The EnDurCrete project website has been created during the early project stage and launched under the domain <http://www.endurcrete.eu>. Webhosting was bought in provider WEDOS, registration data are given in Figure 1 and Figure 2. Following programming languages were used during the website creation: html, php, database MySQL, Java Script and reduction system based on the Open Force.

Information

Order No.	3218001500
Status	active
Ordered	04.01.2018 16:58:39
Created	05.01.2018 04:43:35
Expiration	05.01.2019 (299 days) (renew)
Operating system	Linux
WWW size *	1 MB
E-mails size *	1 MB
Database size *	0 MB
Accounting without VAT	no
Before expiration	request for payment with notifications

support IPv6 (AAAA records)

 only if the domain uses our DNS servers
[\(more info about IPv6\)](#)

Internal Web address:
<http://181781.w61.wedos.ws/>

Services addresses

WWW IPv4	89.221.213.17
WWW IPv6	
FTP	181781.w61.wedos.net
MX	wes1-mx1.wedos.net wes1-mx2.wedos.net wes1-mx-backup.wedos.net
SMTP(S)	smtp-181781.m81.wedos.net
IMAP(S)	imap-181781.m81.wedos.net
POP3(S)	pop-181781.m81.wedos.net
Webmail	https://webmail.wedos.net/

Our DNS servers:
 ns.wedos.net
 ns.wedos.eu
 ns.wedos.cz
 ns.wedos.com

NSSET to CZ.NIC WEDOS

[Webmail](#)
[WebFTP](#)

FTP accounts [create new]

login	status
w181781	active

Database [create new]

No database on this webhosting

Aliases [manage aliases]

Webhosting has no alias

E-mail boxes [manage mailboxes] [e-mail settings]

name
info
petra.topolcanova

Optional services activated [service settings]

name
CRON+
Extra package
HTTPS domain (SNI)

Figure 1: Webhosting registration data

Information	
Order number	3118005680
Status	active
Webhosting	endurcrete.eu [3218001500]
Ordered	04.01.2018 16:55:19
Established	05.01.2018 04:38:49
Expiration	05.01.2019 (299 days) (renew)
Accounting without VAT	no
TLD	eu (EURid)
Owner contact	c28739044
KEYSET ID	wedos
Before expiration	request for payment with notifications

DNS servers [change DNS servers] [edit DNS records]		
Server	IPv4	IPv6
ns.wedos.com		
ns.wedos.eu		
ns.wedos.cz		
ns.wedos.net		

Figure 2: Domain registration data

3 Website description

The website has been set up under the address www.enudrcrete.eu. The site is hosted by FENIX. It has been designed to quickly address the key questions that external visitors to the website are expected to have:

- What is the project about?
- What is the project progress?
- Who is participating in the project?
- What additional details are available?
- Who to contact for more information?

The site itself is split into two sections - private and public. Both sections are described in this document. Main sections of the public part:

- general information about the project,
- partners' details,
- list of events and news,
- all public documents generated during the project,
- links to social network profiles,
- newsletter subscription,
- contact information,
- photo gallery.

The second part of the website is a private section that is available to the FENIX (as an administrator) and to the project partners. The private section can be accessed via log-in credentials. This restricted section will be used for storage of:

- information about meetings,
- deliverables and management reports,
- administrative documents and forms,
- planned publications,
- work packages,
- templates and promo material,
- other documents.

The website is planned to provide information available to the wide public. In the following subsections the single elements - sections and their intended use will be described.

3.1 Home page

The Home page of the EnDurCrete website contains basic information about project. The upper part of the screen shows a navigation panel, using a horizontal structure that is commonly used. At the top of the page the project's logo with the project acronym are placed, as the user scrolls the page down, shortened sections of the actual pages such as "About the Project", latest "News & Events", and "Partners" are listed. These parts of the home page are used as links to the actual pages, where the full content is displayed. The bottom of the home page includes EU logo, funding statement, and subscribe button for the Newsletter.

Figure 3: Home page section

3.2 “About the project” page

Page “About the project” presents the overall concept, objectives, and demo-sites of the project.

endurcrete Home About the project Documents News & Events Gallery Partners Reserved Area Contact

EnDurCrete concept is based on the following novel technologies and tools

- **Novel cement**, by including sustainable, high-quality supplementary cementitious materials (classified coal combustion fly ashes and ground granulated blast furnace slag).
- **New smart fillers** based on nano-modified clays, for anti-corrosion properties and based on micro carbon-based materials (such as carbonaceous inerts like char and the finer fraction of a used foundry sand, derived from industrial by-products) for mechanical and self-sensing properties. The structural self-sensing properties will be complemented with environmental sensors casted in concrete.
- **Advanced non-destructive continuous monitoring and testing tools and procedures**, including technologies tuned for the self-sensing concrete systems. Durability properties of the components will be assessed and monitored. The new developed tools will be integrated by conventional durability testing procedures.
- **New multifunctional coatings** enabling concrete self-healing properties based on resin microencapsulation and protecting both concrete and rebar from aggressive agents.
- **Concrete non-metallic multifunctional reinforcing systems**, based on technical textiles integrated with optical-fibre sensors, enabling both structural reinforcement and continuous structural health monitoring. The systems will be optimised aiming at a proper trade-off between productivity, robustness, and concrete reinforcement adhesion.
- **Coupled experimental and computational approach for theoretical and experimental understanding of factors affecting durability**. Modelling and simulations applied at micro-mesoscale are carried out defining representative elementary volumes of cement paste, mortar, and concrete as well as modelling applied at macroscale is performed representing the whole concrete infrastructures. These continuum models are solved by finite elements analysis. The combined experimental and computational approach will enable long-term durability assessment and resulting service life prediction of the target infrastructures exposed to severe environment.

Overall concept at a glance

- Sustainable durable cement
- Self healing and self-monitoring fillers and coatings
- Sensorized non-metallic reinforcing system
- Durability modelling.

Figure 4: About the project section

3.3 “Documents” page

The “Documents” page is split into subsections Promo material, Presentations, Newsletters, Publications, Papers, Reports and Other. Subsections can be added based on the project requirements at any time by the administrator (FENIX). The Documents page will contain all material that will be published and is thus publicly available (respecting copyright issues).

Figure 5: Public documents section

“News & Events” page

This page will present a list of news and events, which will include all meetings of the project partners and important events in which members of the consortium partners participate, such as conferences, fairs, workshops, etc. Shortened version of this page including approx. three latest news will be shown also on the home page.

Figure 6: News & Events section

3.4 Partners

The “Partners” section will be shown as an interactive panel on the home page. When a user clicks on an individual partner's logo, a table with a short partner description and a hyperlink to the website appears.

Figure 7: Partners section

Figure 8: Partners section - detail

3.5 “Contact” page

The last part of the public section contains contact information of the Project coordinator. It is intended for any inquiries by interested parties.

Figure 9: Contact section

3.6 Reserved area

The reserved area is accessed only by the project partners. Full access could be also granted to the European Commission Officer, if necessary at any time. In this section, the partners can login using their individual access data. Each partner will be provided with a username and password in order

to validate their access to the secure area. In this section the administrator (FENIX) can manage to update section News and Events, upload public and private documents, upload pictures to the Gallery and make changes of the website content. The project partners are enabled to upload and manage private documents.

Figure 10: Reserved Area section – Login

Figure 11: Reserved Area - Restricted files

3.7 Social network links and Newsletter subscription

Social network profiles were created within the online campaign and linked to the website via icons attached to the side. Social profiles used are LinkedIn, Facebook, and Twitter. The website also contains also online Twitter feed which shows the latest Twitter posts and invites the users to visit the Twitter profile. Newsletter subscription is linked to the info@endurcrete.eu where all subscribers are collected for the Newsletter campaign.

Figure 12: Social media and Newsletter subscription

3.8 Cookies policy

Cookies are small text files stored on users' computer by their browser. They have many applications, such as: tracking users as they navigate around a website; remembering user preferences; auto-logins for visitors coming back to a site; and website security. Website cookies policy was automatically implemented to the EnDurCrete website.

Figure 13: Cookies policy

3.9 Working with the website

Figure 14: Working with the website Schema

4 Future development

Short term development of the website under consideration at the time of deliverable writing include:

- monitoring website statistics (new visitors, return visitors, languages, countries of origin, etc.)
- update of website content based on project progress monthly (and on demand when it is needed), mostly in the section “News & Events” and “Gallery”.

Long-term development of the website will include:

- Adding a short video introducing the project
- Adding a “Demonstration” page where the further details about the demo-sites and their progress will be presented
- Adding the “Cluster projects” page where the other projects related to the same topic will be shown.

5 Conclusions and recommendations

The EnDurCrete website is a key element of the project's dissemination strategy. This website will ensure the visibility of the project, facilitate the diffusion of the project's results and promote their exploitation. An initial version of the EnDurCrete has been designed, provisioned and deployed on the Internet.

Consisting mostly of static content, it has been designed to quickly answer the key questions that external visitors to the website are expected to have. The project website will continuously form and develop as the project itself grows. The information included on the project website is likely to be valuable even after the project has finished. Therefore, the consortium aims at ensuring that the website will continue to exist after the project funding has finished and that bookmarks and published URLs will continue to function.